

Polarographic behaviour of Cu^{II} -2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin complexes in ethanol-water (65%) media

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Abstract : Polarographic behaviour of 2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin with Cu^{II} ion in 65% ethanol-water media has been investigated. Crow's mean diffusion coefficient (utilizing diffusion current values) and DeFord-Hume's (using half-wave potential values) methods were applied to determine the stability constant values of complexes. Cu^{II} forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with 2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin. The studies were carried out at different temperatures to calculate thermodynamic parameters, the change in Gibb's free energy, change in enthalpy and change in entropy.

Keywords : Polarography, benzoin complexes, stability constant.

Introduction

Complexation behaviour of first row transition metal ions with hydroxy-deoxy-benzoin had been examined by Priyokumar¹, Sharma²⁻⁶ and Sharma and Bennerjee⁷⁻⁹. Potentiometric results showed that the ligand forms 1 : 1 complexes with all the metal ions. During the polarographic investigation (inappreciable change in half-wave potential) on complexation of cations with the ligands (O-HDB and 2,4-DHDB), Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method¹⁰ (using limiting current) gives encouraging results. Polarographic studies of Co^{II} -2-hydroxy-deoxy-benzoin⁸ showed some unusual behaviour while other transition metals form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions form 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes. Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with 2,4-DHDB. In the present work, polarographic behaviour of Cu^{II} with 2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin (2,4,6-THDB) has been studied. Stability constants of the complexes have been calculated by Crow's method¹⁰ and DeFord-Hume's method¹¹. The studies have been carried out at different temperatures to calculate the thermodynamic parameters.

Experimental

All the chemicals, perchloric acid, lithium hydroxide and copper sulphate were of AR grade. Lithium perchlorate was prepared by neutralizing perchloric acid with

lithium hydroxide and then crystallizing the salt from distilled water. The ligand was prepared by taking a solution of phloroglucinol (15 g) and benzyl cyanide (dried and distilled, 15 ml) in anhydrous ether (250 ml), which were added to fused ZnCl_2 (8 g) and the mixture was saturated with anhydrous HCl gas at 268 K. It was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 18 h. The formed ketimine hydrochloride was washed twice with anhydrous ether, dissolved in water (1.0 L) and heated over steam bath for two hours. On cooling 2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin (12 g) separates out as colourless plates². It was recrystallised from water and dried in an air-oven at 363 K for two hours (m.p. 437-438 K). The purity also had been checked by thin layer chromatography.

Stock solution (1.0 mmol dm^{-3}) of 2,4,6-THDB was prepared in purified ethanol⁷. A 10 ml of the test solution contains (a) metal ion (1.0 ml , 1.0 mol m^{-3}), LiClO_4 (1.0 ml , 1.0 mol dm^{-3}), ethanol (6.5 ml) and volume was made upto 10.0 ml with conductivity water, (b) metal ion (1.0 ml , 1.0 mol m^{-3}), LiClO_4 (1.0 ml , 1.0 mol dm^{-3}), increasing volumes of ligand solution in ethanol (metal ligand ratio 1 : 10, 1 : 50, 1 : 100, 1 : 200, 1 : 300, 1 : 400, 1 : 500), additional ethanol to make a total 6.5 ml and water to make upto 10.0 ml volume. The pH of the solutions were adjusted by LiOH or HClO_4 acid solutions before making up to volume. All the solutions were kept

overnight after preparation to attain equilibrium. Solutions were transferred to thermostatted Kalouvek cell (decinormal calomel electrode). Iolar grade-1 nitrogen gas was bubbled for fifteen minutes for purging of oxygen from the solutions and polarograms were recorded using Radiometer Polarograph Polariter PO₄(g). Dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) was made by a Sargent capillary with characteristics $m = 1.688$ mg/s and $t = 4.3$ s at 70 cm. The pH of the solutions were checked before and after recording the polarograms, using ELICO pH-meter LI-120.

Results and discussion

The polarographic reduction of copper in the presence of 2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin gave a well-defined single wave which was diffusion controlled (linear, i_d vs \sqrt{h} plot and i_d vs concentration of Cu^{II} ion, plot passing through the origin). Accordingly the plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs E_{dme} were also linear with a slope 35 ± 1 mV. Thus the cathodic reduction of Cu^{II} in 2,4,6-THDB was diffusion controlled, reversible and involves two

electrons.

With the increasing concentration of ligand the half-wave potential of the wave shifted towards more negative value than the aquo Cu^{II} ion. The negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ showed that the complexation occurred between Cu^{II} ion and 2,4,6-THDB. Diffusion current accordingly decreased with increasing ligand concentration. All the data are shown in Tables 1 and 2 for 298 and 303 K.

Crow's method :

Variation of Δi_d with $\log [L]$ at 298 and 303 K were plotted. By integrating the curves, the function $\log F'_0[L]$ were found for various ligand concentrations and these were plotted against $\log [L]$. Using the limiting slope values¹² and maximum coordination number (spectroscopy) constants K were evaluated. They were at two temperatures, 14.2860 and 10.7124 (K -values). Functions $\log F_0[L]$ were then calculated using the K -values. Finally $F_j [L]$ vs $[L]$ were plotted, from the intercepts on the $F_j [L]$ axis values of formation constants were calculated. The data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Polarographic data of Cu^{II}-2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin system in 65% ethanol-water media by Crow's method
Cu^{II} = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, pH = 6.0, LiClO₄ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, $m = 1.688$ mg/s, $t = 4.3$ s

Sl. no.	Conc. of ligand [L] (mol dm ⁻³)	-log [L]	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (μ A)	Temp. 298 K						
					Slope (mV)	Δi_d (μ A)	$\log F'_0[L]$	$\log F_0[L]$	$F_0[L]$	$F_1[L]$	$F_2[L]$
1.	0.000	-	0.035	0.352	30	-	-	-	1.000	-	-
2.	0.001	3.0	0.040	0.320	35	0.032	0.0273370	0.3905	2.457	-	-
3.	0.005	2.3	0.050	0.302	35	0.050	0.0538537	0.7693	5.879	976	-
4.	0.010	2.0	0.060	0.288	35	0.064	0.0702537	1.0036	10083	908	18800
5.	0.020	1.7	0.075	0.262	35	0.090	0.0924937	1.3214	20.960	998	13900
6.	0.030	1.5	0.085	0.240	30	0.112	0.1128937	1.6128	41.002	1333	20433
7.	0.040	1.4	0.090	0.200	30	0.152	0.1262137	1.8031	63.548	1564	21075
8.	0.050	1.3	0.095	0.192	30	0.160	0.1417337	2.0248	105.877	2097	27540
Temp. 303 K											
1.	0.000	-	0.0325	0.396	30	-	-	-	1.000	-	-
2.	0.001	3.0	0.0400	0.340	35	0.056	0.0512288	0.5488	3.538	-	-
3.	0.005	2.3	0.0500	0.332	35	0.064	0.0849088	0.9096	8.121	1424	-
4.	0.010	2.0	0.0600	0.320	35	0.076	0.1061088	1.1367	13.699	1270	-
5.	0.020	1.7	0.0700	0.298	40	0.098	0.1320688	1.4148	25.989	1249	27450
6.	0.030	1.5	0.0800	0.248	35	0.148	0.1552688	1.6633	46.057	1502	26733
7.	0.040	1.4	0.0850	0.204	35	0.192	0.1732688	1.8562	71.812	1770	26750
8.	0.050	1.3	0.0900	0.196	35	0.200	0.1931488	2.0691	117.246	2325	32500

$\beta_1 = 720, \beta_2 = 20500$
 $\beta_1 = 700, \beta_2 = 26750$

Note

Table 2. Polarographic data of Cu^{II}-2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin system in 65% ethanol-water media by DeFord and Hume's method
Cu^{II} = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, pH = 6.0, LiClO₄ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, m = 1.688 mg/s, t = 4.3 s

Sl. no.	Conc. of ligand [L] (mol dm ⁻³)	-log [L]	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (μA)	Temp. 298 K					
					Slope (mV)	ΔE _{1/2} (V)	log I _M /I _C	F ₀ [L]	F ₁ [L]	F ₂ [L]
1.	0.000	-	0.035	0.352	30	-	-	1.000	-	-
2.	0.001	3.0	0.040	0.320	35	0.0050	0.0414	1.600	-	-
3.	0.005	2.3	0.050	0.302	35	0.0150	0.0665	3.758	551.6	70200
4.	0.010	2.0	0.060	0.288	35	0.0250	0.0872	8.603	760.3	56000
5.	0.020	1.7	0.075	0.262	35	0.0400	0.1282	30.488	1474.0	63700
6.	0.030	1.5	0.085	0.240	30	0.0500	0.1663	72.647	2388.0	72933
7.	0.040	1.4	0.090	0.200	30	0.0550	0.2455	128.797	3195.0	74875
8.	0.050	1.3	0.095	0.192	30	0.0600	0.2632	198.197	3944.0	74880
Temp. 303 K										
1.	0.000	-	0.0325	0.396	30	-	-	1.000	-	-
2.	0.001	3.0	0.0400	0.340	35	0.0075	0.0662	2.091	-	-
3.	0.005	2.3	0.0500	0.332	35	0.0175	0.0766	4.675	735.0	-
4.	0.010	2.0	0.0600	0.320	35	0.0275	0.0925	10.585	958.0	-
5.	0.020	1.7	0.0700	0.298	40	0.0375	0.1235	24.813	1191.0	50800
6.	0.030	1.5	0.0800	0.249	35	0.0475	0.2032	65.068	2136.0	65366
7.	0.040	1.4	0.0850	0.204	35	0.0525	0.2881	116.886	2897.0	68050
8.	0.050	1.3	0.0900	0.196	35	0.0575	0.3054	179.702	3574.0	67980

β₁ = 200, β₂ = 74000

β₁ = 175, β₂ = 68000

Deford and Hume's method :

Table 2 provides the stability constant values for the complexes calculated using DeFord and Hume's¹¹ method.

The thermodynamic parameters calculated are given in Table 3.

Conclusion :

Copper(II) forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with 2,4,6-

THDB confirmed by Crow¹⁰ and DeFord and Hume¹¹ methods. In both the cases the order of stability constant values is similar. Thermodynamic parameters change in Gibb's free-energy was negative showing the spontaneous process, change in enthalpy was also negative predicting exothermic reaction, and change in entropy was positive showing highly disordered reaction.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of Cu^{II}-2,4,6-trihydroxy-deoxy-benzoin system in 65% ethanol-water media (LiClO₄ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³)

Temp. (K)	Method	β _j	log K _j	-ΔG [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-ΔH [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS [#] (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
298	Crow's	β ₁ = 720	2.86	16.32	6.92	31.54
		β ₂ = 20.5 × 10 ³	1.45	8.27		
	DeFord and Hume's	β ₁ = 200	2.30	13.12	2.08	37.05
		β ₂ = 74.0 × 10 ³	2.57	14.66		
303	Crow's	β ₁ = 700	2.84	16.48		
		β ₂ = 26.7 × 10 ³	1.59	9.22		
	DeFord and Hume's	β ₁ = 175	2.24	12.99		
		β ₂ = 68.0 × 10 ³	2.59	15.03		

[#]Activity is less than unit value.

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